

Stochastic Parrots and Clinical Reality: Epistemic Obligation and the Decline of Biological Plausibility

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Abstract

Background: The current reliance on medical Big Data is producing a *mostro ibrido* (monstrous hybrid) of statistical significance that lacks biological anchoring. This investigation builds upon the framework of epistemic injustice and epistemic obligation from (Herzog and Branford, 2025) to analyze the systemic marginalization of human expertise in computational medicine.

Methods: This work performs a critical audit of three high-profile studies where algorithmic outputs generated from large-scale databases stand in direct contradiction to national gold standards and established clinical benchmarks.

Results: The analysis reveals profound discrepancies, including the disappearance of approximately 50,000 cancer cases per year in a nationwide database and the creation of statistically significant but biologically impossible correlations. These findings demonstrate that: a) the epistemic obligation toward algorithms compels practitioners to ignore clinical common sense in favor of bureaucratized data mirages, b) medical AI often operates as a stochastic parrot, capable of recombining vast amounts of data into seemingly coherent patterns that possess no actual contact with underlying pathological truths.

Conclusion: This investigation denounces the definitive farewell to the proof of causality in favor of a mechanized version of medical truth. It highlights the urgent necessity to reclaim epistemic agency, arguing that biological reality cannot be fully replaced by a database, regardless of its scale. We must prevent the statistical ghost of a database from replacing the living patient in the clinical decision-making process.

Keywords: Big medical Data, Epistemic Injustice, Biological Plausibility, Medical AI, Algorithmic Auditing

1. Introduction: Beyond Relational Ethics in Computational Medicine

In their recent contribution, Herzog and Branford (Herzog and Branford, 2025) provide a compelling relational ethics approach to the deployment of Artificial Intelligence in medicine, identifying a critical **epistemic obligation** that compels practitioners to defer to algorithmic outputs. They argue that “*AI-based decision support risks excluding patients and medical personnel from relevant epistemic processes vital to good medical practice*”. While we fully resonate with their ethical concerns, this article contends that the crisis is not merely relational but deeply rooted in the technical and statistical foundations of current Big medical Data. Our intervention is intended to move beyond philosophical insights and investigate the hard, and often contradictory, reality of computational medicine.

We contend that the epistemic oppression identified by Herzog and Branford is rooted in an epistemological deeper crisis: the transformation of statistical inference into a black box, a mechanized guillotine that severs the connection between data and clinical meaning. Rather than proposing a purely technical fix, this study advocates for a return to auditing through clinical plausibility, where a statistical coefficient is no longer allowed to override the pulse of the patient and the specific clinical references that constitute the historical and empirical record of human pathology. By examining the divergence between algorithmic outputs and national gold standards, this investigation seeks to expose how the erosion of biological plausibility leads to a bureaucratized version of medical truth.

2. Background: The Mostro Ibrido and the Fury of the New

To understand this structural injustice, we must recognize that modern science has birthed a mostro ibrido (better said monstrous hybrid). In 1925, when Ronald Fisher (Fisher, 1925) published *Statistical Methods for Research Workers*, he did not intend the p-value to be an on/off proof of truth. For Fisher, the p-value was an *index of surprise*. If one obtained $p < 0.05$, the signal was: “*This result is unusual enough to suggest that something interesting is happening here*”. It was never a verdict; it was an invitation to replicate the experiment, to reproduce the results elsewhere or otherwise, a signpost suggesting that the matter deserved further investigation. Statistical significance was a gateway to reproducibility, not a final destination. If a result is not reproducible, that initial $p < 0.05$ is merely a stroke of luck, just a Type I error.

This investigation contends that the modern chaos stems from the forced fusion of two rival schools of thought. While Fisher viewed the p-value as a continuous measure of evidence, Neyman and Pearson introduced a rigid, binary decision-threshold (α) designed for mechanical accept/reject choices (Neyman and Pearson 1933). Today, researchers (and scientific journal editors, as well) live within this hybrid monster: they perform Fisher’s calculations but apply Neyman-Pearson’s mechanical guillotine. This has generated a *p-value culture* where the difference between publishing in *The Lancet* or discarding a year of work lies in the trivial gap between a p of 0.049 and 0.051.

This cultural shift has inverted the Popperian ideal of science (Popper, 1959). For Karl Popper, the scientist's duty was to attempt to tear down their own theories, to falsify them. Today's researcher, armed with Big Data, no longer asks, "*Can I prove this idea wrong?*" but rather "*How much data must I add until I am shown to be right?*" We have moved from falsification to data-dredging, where the goal is to find that tiny fragment of signal that allows one to shout: "*εὕρηκα (Heurēka): I found it!*"

In the era of Big Data, rejecting the null hypothesis has become trivial. When the sample size (N) is enormous, even an irrelevant difference or a systematic error can produce a statistically significant p-value. We have confused statistical significance (a mathematical calculation) with scientific and biological significance, i.e., the reality of the facts. This study argues that this surrender to the *furia del nuovo* (better said, fury of the new) and *neofilia scientifica* is driven by a system where academic journals and media outlets prioritize the discovery of new, because that is where the business lies. A paper stating, "*We checked and found no difference between the groups (the null hypothesis holds)*" is often rejected as uninformative. Conversely, a paper claiming, "*We found a link between X and Y*", even if biologically impossible or based on inconsistent data or not easily reproducible, is rushed to the cover of prestigious journals.

This represents the ultimate epistemic injustice analyzed in this work: rewarding the mirage of the new, while punishing the rigor of clinical reality. This phenomenon is fueled by a systemic obsession with novel associations, and farewell to the proof of causality, that attract high-impact publications. As the sample size grows to millions, the index of surprise vanishes; every minor noise becomes a significant signal. The mechanized guillotine cuts through the complexity of the patient's lifeworld, replacing it with a mathematical significance that often masks a biological absurdity. We have traded the Popperian ideal of falsification (Popper, 1959) for a culture of data-dredging, where a black box filled of data is interrogated until it confesses a narrative that satisfies the industry's neophilia. This Big Data mirage creates the illusion of certainty through sheer volume, masking the technical depths of its internal contradictions. When, for example, the database ignores national disease registries or clinical benchmarks, it creates a reality that exists only inside the server (or the sample of data collected for that specific retrospective analysis). This leads to a kind of solitude of the clinician. Practitioners are forced into an epistemic obligation to trust a machine that claims a 77% reduction in a disease, even when their own eyes and the historical record say otherwise. Truth is no longer verified against the human body, but against the internal consistency of a (flawed) database.

3. Results: Inside the Black Box vs. Outside in the World

To provide concrete weight to these claims, this article presents a critical investigation of three recent cases where the algorithmic machine, relying solely on medical Big Data, has extrapolated clinical conclusions that stand in direct contradiction to reality. By reality, we mean here the confrontation with gold standards, best practices, and clinical common sense,

the neglect of which has caused distortions in media narratives and hesitation among decision-makers.

The following analysis demonstrates that what is true inside the black box is not necessarily true outside of it, and requires rigorous empirical demonstration. In doing so, we intend no disrespect toward the authors of these works, whose scientific commitment we fully respect; rather, we aim to expose the structural flaws that emerge when statistical power is decoupled from biological plausibility.

3.1 Case A: The “Epistemic Exclusion” or the Disappearing Population

This study identifies a profound instance of epistemic exclusion, a concept proposed by Herzog and Branford. This exclusion is most evident when the black box produces findings that are biologically impossible, yet are accepted because of their statistical power. This is exactly the case of a recent analysis of the South Korean database regarding cancer incidence (Kim et al., 2025).

Using nearly 3 million records from that database, the study suggests a rising cancer risk among the COVID-19 vaccinated. However, a fundamental check against the gold standards of national statistics reveals a staggering paradox. The study's raw figures measure an all-cancer incidence, of 40.78 cases per 10,000 individuals, but the official national average says that over the latest years the all-cancer South Korean cases were as many as 52.46 per 10,000 (Kang et al., 2023; Park et al., 2024; Park et al., 2025), the study's cohort deviates downwards by over 22%. We have reached here this paradox: the much-debated COVID-19 vaccination supposedly increased the number of cancer cases among the vaccinated compared to the unvaccinated, yet overall it protected South Koreans against cancer because it lowered the total incidence.

In simpler words, our investigation reveals that inside the black box of the original study, approximately 50,000 cancer cases per year simply vanished (Rocchetti, 2025a). This is the technical depth of the mirage: the study's population was bureaucratically cleaned to the point of clinical irrelevance. This represents a form of hermeneutical injustice: using the authority of millions to mask a sample that defies the biological reality of an entire country.

3.2. Case B: The “Epistemic Obligation” or Erasing the Peaks of Reality

Our present analysis further explores the case of the epistemic obligation that compels practitioners to prioritize algorithmic outputs over their own clinical expertise. This obligation becomes a trap when the signal generated by the machine is a byproduct of structural bias rather than biological truth. A prime example is the reported link between COVID-19 vaccination and Vitiligo (Kim HJ et al., 2024), which claims an augmented risk among vaccinated individuals (Hazard Ratio of 2.714), again using some millions of health records.

However an auditing of the data (Rocchetti, 2025b) reveals the bias hidden in the age gap: the Vaccinated cohort was 11 years older than the Non-Vaccinated group. Since Vitiligo incidence peaks after age 50, the black box artificially maximized the signal by ignoring this distribution. Furthermore, the control group's incidence was 70% lower than the national Gold Standard of 2.21 per 10,000 (Kang and Lee, 2023). Under the epistemic obligation to trust the p-value of the original study, the clinician is forced to accept a signal that vanishes once the demographic mirage is corrected.

3.3. Case C: The “Erosion of Epistemic Agency” or the Implausible Miracle

This third case exemplifies what Herzog and Branford have described as the erosion of epistemic agency. When the machine produces a result that contradicts the foundational principles of human pathology, the clinician’s ability to intervene as a rational agent is stifled by the overwhelming authority of the database.

Exactly like in the case of a multi-million individuals neuropsychiatric cohort of (Kim HJ et al., 2024b), a retrospective study of which reports an incredible 77% reduction in Schizophrenia risk (HR = 0.231) after COVID-19 vaccination. This miracle defies the stable epidemiological dynamics of chronic psychiatric disorders. Comparing these findings against the South Korean gold standard we find a critical deficit: the vaccinated group's incidence (circa 0.60) was vastly lower than the national benchmark of 2.07 per 10,000 population (Cho et al., 2020; Rocchetti, 2025c). The algorithm perceived protection simply because the database failed to record the existing cases. Our analysis denounces that to accept this result is to surrender one's epistemic agency to a bureaucratization of truth that has lost all contact with the clinical reality of mental health.

4. Discussion: Reclaiming Common Sense in the Age of AI and Big data

The evidence presented in this investigation leads to a definitive conclusion: To move from epistemic oppression to epistemic inclusion, we must treat medical AI as a mediator, not a master. Our present study demonstrates that opening the black box does not require complex new bureaucracies, but rather a return to the best practices of auditing algorithmic outputs against gold standards and the plausibility of clinical experience.

We have argued throughout this work that the scientific community must have the courage to declare that a study is not better simply because its database is larger. Size does not excuse a violation of biological plausibility. By confronting the math with the same rigor we apply to ethical principles, we reclaim the clinician's role in the meaning-making process.

We acknowledge certain limitations in our study. As a critical investigation based on case-audit, this work does not aim to provide a comprehensive statistical re-analysis of all existing medical Big Data, nor does it dismiss the undeniable potential of large-scale datasets in medicine for retrospective studies. Rather, its scope is limited to exposing specific, high-profile instances where the decoupling of statistical significance from biological plausibility

has led to evident clinical paradoxes. Furthermore, while we rely on national gold standards as a benchmark for truth, we recognize that these registries themselves are subject to reporting delays and bureaucratic constraints. However, the magnitude of the discrepancies identified, such as the vanishing of entire patient populations, suggests a structural flaw that transcends simple reporting lag.

Nonetheless, our analysis highlights the pervasive, everyday risk of becoming lost in the labyrinth of medical Big Data, where countless inferences are algorithmically deduced but remain unvalidated by a confrontation with reality. We must remain vigilant in recognizing that biological reality does not yet, and perhaps never will, coincide 100% with a database, or even a specific fragment of it, regardless of its scale. To mistake the digital sample for the clinical whole is to succumb to a mirage that replaces the living patient with a statistical parrot.

Finally, we contend and reiterate that the international scientific community must demand that these databases be made public and accessible for independent auditing. Only through such transparency can we transform the black box of Big Data from a tool of statistical oppression into a shared resource for human flourishing, grounded in the common sense of clinical reality. Reclaiming epistemic agency is not just a philosophical necessity; it is a clinical obligation to prevent the definitive erosion of medical truth.

5. Conclusion: From Statistical Mirage to Epistemic Integrity

This investigation has demonstrated that the current crisis in computational medicine is, at its core, a crisis of biological anchoring. By auditing three high-profile cases, we have exposed how the epistemic obligation toward Big Data has allowed a bureaucratized truth to supersede the historical and empirical reality of human pathology.

Our analysis of the investigated datasets reveals that the sheer scale of modern databases acts as a double-edged sword: while it provides unprecedented statistical power, it simultaneously creates a black box where entire patient populations can bureaucratically vanish, and where biological miracles, such as a 77% reduction in schizophrenia, are manufactured by data-dredging rather than clinical reality. This represents the ultimate epistemic injustice: the systematic marginalization of human expertise in favor of an algorithm that, despite its millions of records, functions as a “stochastic parrot” devoid of clinical common sense.

We conclude that the proof of causality cannot be replaced by the fury of the new or the index of surprise provided by the p-value. To reclaim epistemic agency, the scientific community must enforce a return to biological plausibility as the final arbiter of truth. A statistical coefficient must never again be allowed to override the national gold standards and the lived experience of clinicians.

Finally, the restoration of medical truth demands transparency. We reiterate our call for the public accessibility of the underlying databases to allow for independent international auditing. Only by grounding our computational tools in the common sense of clinical reality can we

prevent the definitive erosion of medicine into a mere branch of administrative accounting. The duty of the researcher is not to make the data confess, but to ensure that the data still speaks for the patient.

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